

Risk-based remaining life assessment of corrosion affected reinforced concrete structural members

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Remaining life assessment of corrosion affected reinforced concrete structural members is a topic of current R&D worldwide. There is an urgent need to develop more scientific and rational methodologies for this purpose. Number of investigations have already been carried out to assess the damage/distress due to corrosion, that would help in remaining life assessment. While most of these studies are deterministic in nature, efforts are also being made to use probabilistic methods for damage assessment. However, an important aspect in remaining life estimation is the interpretation of the data related to damage/distress and making expert judgement about damage/distress level. Due consideration needs to be given to the quality of the data and the expert interpreting the data. In this paper, expert judgement regarding corrosion damage level is integrated with the structural risk, expressed in terms of probability of attaining a particular damage level, for the remaining life assessment of corrosion affected reinforced concrete structural members. In the proposed methodology, the thinking process of the expert, in corrosion damage assessment, is modelled within a probabilistic framework using Brunswikian theory. The performance of each expert is determined by computing the achievement index. The damage assessment procedure is integrated with Markov Chain model for risk-based remaining life assessment. To illustrate the usefulness of the proposed methodology in determining more rationally the remaining life, an example problem of remaining life assessment of a reinforced concrete bridge girder is considered.

The corrosion of reinforcement in concrete is an issue of major concern, as it affects the safety (due to the reduction in area of reinforcement) and serviceability (due to the formation of rust stains, cracking and spalling) of the structure. The premature deterioration of reinforced concrete (rc) structures has necessitated the need for continual structural health monitoring (SHM) to determine the existence, location and extent (or degree) of corrosion damage, if any, on the structure. SHM is the process of establishing some knowledge of the current condition of the structure or its components¹, which is required for the performance evaluation of the structure. While SHM is a part of the value chain as proposed by Wong and Yao², the information obtained from SHM needs to be processed further for quantifying the risk, which is an important link in the value chain. As pointed out by Wong and Yao², there exists a gap between where SHM currently stops and where financial decision (remaining useful life) begins, and this gap needs to be filled. This requires the rational assessment of the current damage state based on the data from SHM, and the remaining life estimation using structural risk as the norm. A rational estimation of the current condition and remaining life will help in making engineering decisions

regarding inspection/maintenance activities for the structure.

A reliable method for service life estimation of the structure is a pre-requisite for remaining life assessment. Systematic approaches/methodologies for service life prediction have been proposed by various researchers/codes of practice^{3–5}. Expert judgement is identified as an important part of evaluation in most of these methodologies. For instance, the methodology of RILEM TC 31-PCM emphasizes expert judgement as an essential part of evaluation, and points out that ‘the complexity of evaluating the interaction of materials or systems with their environment requires expertise that cannot be fully replaced by existing test methods’³. It also identifies the use of methods of social-, health-, psychological-, natural- and technical sciences for the expert judgement.

CIBW80/RILEM 71-PSL³ pointed out that there is a requirement for an effective mechanism for obtaining and reporting data on in-service performance of structures. Also, it may be difficult to handle the large amount of data acquired from continuous SHM manually. A suitably created database of KBS would help in handling this amount of data through proper acquisition, representation and

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